

Lexical Sense Alignment using Weighted Bipartite b -Matching

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1 Introduction

Lexical resources are important components of natural language processing (NLP) applications providing linguistic information about the vocabulary of a language and the semantic relationships between the words. While there is an increasing number of lexical resources, particularly expert-made ones such as WordNet [8] or FrameNet [2], as well as collaboratively-curated ones such as Wikipedia¹ or Wiktionary², manual construction and maintenance of such resources is a cumbersome task. This can be efficiently addressed by NLP techniques. Aligned resources have shown to improve word, knowledge and domain coverage and increase multilingualism by creating new lexical resources such as Yago [13], BabelNet [9] and ConceptNet [12]. In addition, they can improve the performance of NLP tasks such as word sense disambiguation [10], semantic role tagging [15] and semantic relations extraction [14].

2 Objective

One of the current challenges in aligning lexical data across different resources is word sense alignment (WSA). Different monolingual resources may use different wordings and structures for the same concepts and entries. There are various approaches in aligning definitional texts based on semantic similarity and linking techniques. For instance, Meyer and Gurevych [7] use semantic similarity and Personalized PageRank (PPR) to estimate the semantic relatedness in linking Wiktionary and WordNet. Pilehvar and Navigli [11] go beyond the surface form semantic similarity by transforming resources into semantic networks. Differently, Matuschek and Gurevych [5] present Dijkstra-WSA algorithm which aligns word senses using Dijkstra's shortest path algorithm.

In this study, we present a similarity-based approach for WSA in English WordNet and Wiktionary with a focus on the polysemous items. Our approach relies on semantic textual similarity using features such as string distance metrics and word embeddings, and a graph matching algorithm. Transforming the alignment problem into a bipartite graph matching enables us to apply graph matching algorithms, in particular, weighted bipartite b -matching (WB b M).

¹ <https://www.wikipedia.org/>

² <https://www.wiktionary.org/>

3 Method

WBbM is one of the widely studied classical problems in combinatorial optimization for modeling data management applications, e-commerce and resource allocation systems [1, 3, 4]. WBbM is a variation of the weighted bipartite matching, also known as assignment problem. In the assignment problem, the optimal matching only contains one-to-one matching with the highest weight sum. This bijective mapping restriction is not realistic in the case of lexical resources where an entry may be linked to more than one entries. Therefore, WBbM aims at providing a more diversified matching where a node may be connected to a certain number of nodes. Formally, given $G = ((U, V), E)$ with weights W and vertex-labelling functions $L : U \cup V \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ and $B : U \cup V \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, WBbM finds a subgraph $H = ((U, V), E')$ which maximizes $\sum_{e \in E'} W(e)$ having $u \in [L(u), B(u)]$ and $v \in [L(v), B(v)]$. In other words, the number of the edges that can be connected to a node is determined by the lower and upper bound functions L and B , respectively.

Algorithm 1: Greedy WBbM

Input: $G = ((U, V), E, W)$, bounds L and B

Output: $H = ((U, V), E', W)$ satisfying bound constraints with a greedily-maximized score $\sum_{e \in E'} W(e)$

- 1 $E' = \emptyset$
 - 2 Sort E by descending $W(e)$
 - 3 **for** e **to** E **do**
 - 4 **if** $H = ((U, V), E' \cup \{e\}, W)$ *does not violate* L *and* B **then**
 - 5 $E' = E' \cup \{e\}$
 - 6 **return** $H = ((U, V), E', W)$
-

Algorithm 1 presents the WBbM algorithm with a greedy approach where an edge is selected under the condition that adding such an edge does not violate the lower and the upper bounds, i.e. L and B .

■ **Figure 1** Sense alignment system

We evaluate the performance of our approach on aligning sense definitions in WordNet and Wiktionary using an aligned resource presented by Meyer and Gurevych [7]. Given an identical entry in English WordNet and Wiktionary, we first convert the senses to a bipartite graph where each side of the graph represents the senses belonging to one resource. Then, we extract the similarity scores between those senses using a similarity function. The similarity function is a trained model based on similarity features such as word length ratio, longest common subsequence, Jaccard measure, word embeddings and forward precision, which is performed by NASIC [6]. And finally, the senses in the the weighted bipartite graph are matched by the WBbM algorithm. This process is illustrated in Figure 1 where senses of entry E_i in resource \mathcal{R}_1 , $\{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n\}$, are aligned with the senses of the same entry in \mathcal{R}_2 , $\{S'_1, S'_2, \dots, S'_n\}$. The lower and upper bounds of the right side and left side of the graph, respectively $[l, b]$ and $[l', b']$, are the parameters to be tuned.

4 Evaluation

In order to evaluate the performance of our alignment approach, we calculated macro precision P_{macro} , macro recall R_{macro} , average F-measure F_{avg} and average accuracy A_{avg} as follows:

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad P_{macro} = \frac{1}{|E|} \sum_{i=1}^{|E|} \frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FP_i} \quad (1)$$

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad R_{macro} = \frac{1}{|E|} \sum_{i=1}^{|E|} \frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FN_i} \quad (2)$$

$$F = 2 \times \frac{P \times R}{P + R} \quad F_{avg} = \frac{1}{|E|} \sum_{i=1}^{|E|} F_i \quad (3)$$

$$A_{avg} = \frac{1}{|E|} \sum_{i=1}^{|E|} \frac{TP_i + TN_i}{TP_i + TN_i + FP_i + FN_i} \quad (4)$$

where E refers to the set of entries, TP, TN, FN and FP respectively refer to true positive, true negative, false negative and false positive.

Table 1 provides the evaluation results using the WBbM algorithm with different combinations of the matching bounds over the left side (WordNet senses) and the right side (Wiktionary senses) of the alignment graph. We observe that a higher upper bound increases the recall. On the other hand, setting the lower bound to 1 provides a higher precision, while parameters with a lower bound of 0, e.g. $[0, 3]$, lack precision. Note that $[0, 1]$ parameter performs similarly as a bijective mapping algorithms such as the assignment problem where a node can be only matched to one node. Our approach delivers superior results in comparison to the baseline results provided by McCrae and Buitelaar [6].

Left bound, right bound	P_{macro}	R_{macro}	F_{avg}	A_{avg}
[0, 1], [0, 1]	81.86	61.83	68.51	69.48
[0, 2], [0, 1]	78.13	70.74	73.28	76.57
[0, 3], [0, 1]	77.88	71.38	73.59	77.13
[1, 2], [1, 2]	81.21	74.17	76.59	79.49
[1, 3], [1, 3]	81.26	75.02	77.12	80.14
[1, 5], [0, 1]	81.25	75.25	77.28	80.33
[1, 5], [1, 2]	81.25	75.23	77.26	80.32

■ **Table 1** WbM algorithm performance on alignment of WordNet and Wiktionary

5 Conclusion

We revisited WordNet-Wiktionary alignment task and proposed an approach based on textual and semantic similarity and WbM algorithm. We demonstrated that this approach is efficient for aligning resources in comparison to the baseline results thanks to the flexibility of the matching algorithm. However, tuning the parameters of the matching algorithm needs further investigations of the resource and is not following a rule. In future work, we plan to extend our experiments to more resources.

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